

Condensation of Bromal Hydrate with Aliphatic Amides.

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Although the chloral amide derivatives have been studied carefully, less work has been done on the corresponding compounds of bromalamides, in spite of their physiological importance. Bischoff prepared bromalurethane (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 628) and Schiff and Tassinari bromalacetamide (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1786).

In the work here described, a series of aliphatic amides from formamide up to pelargonamide, have been condensed with bromal hydrate and the properties of the products have been compared with those of the corresponding chloral derivatives.

The bromalamides are obtained by mixing excess of bromal hydrate with the amide and heating until a solid is formed. The reaction proceeds as follows:—

Cold sodium hydroxide solution converts them into bromoform and the corresponding amide. The higher members of the series react more slowly.

The bromalamides differ from the chloralamides in some respects. They can be divided into two groups: (i) Formamide to butyramide, (ii) valeramide to pelargonamide.

Compounds of the group (i) are more reactive and the reduction products less stable than those of the group (ii). The chloral compounds of the group (i) are more readily formed than those of the group (ii). Bromalformamide is obtained only with concentrated sulphuric acid as the condensing agent. With sodium hydroxide, the bromal compounds of the first group decompose more readily than those of the chloral compounds.

The presence of the OH group in the condensation products gives rise to a number of derivatives such as, acetyl, benzoyl, methoxy and anhydro.

Action of acetic anhydride.—By treating the condensation products with acetic anhydride in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid the acetyl derivatives are obtained, while in presence of dilute sodium hydroxide at 0°, the anhydro compounds are the main products provided the final mixture remains acidic. It has been found that the acetyl derivatives of the group (ii) viz., acetyl-, onanth-, capryl-, and pelargonamides are very easily prepared by Chattaway's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2495).

Action of dimethyl sulphate.—Owing to the unstability of the bromal compounds in presence of alkali, the methylation was carried out at 0° (*cf.* Feist, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 945); bromalformamide could not be methylated at all. Methylation takes place more readily with the compounds of the group (ii).

As the condensation products, when treated with two molecules of phosphorus pentachloride, give rise to the compounds of the type (I) they probably exist in tautomeric forms (II) and (III) (*cf.* Schiff and Tassinari, *loc. cit.*).

The constitution of the reduction products of the bromalamides has been discussed by Yelburgi and Wheeler in a paper communicated to this journal.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Bromal formamide.—Formamide (8 g.) and bromal hydrate (58 g.) were heated together till a clear solution was formed. It was cooled, mixed with a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid, left for 2—3 days, poured over crushed ice and then kept in the refrigerator for about 6 hours. The product crystallised as tiny plates from methyl alcohol, m. p. 139-40°, yield 18 g. Unlike the other bromal amides, it is soluble in water. (Found: Br, 73·5. $\text{C}_3\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{NBr}_3$ requires Br, 73·6 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, obtained in the usual manner, crystallised in needles, m. p. 107-8°. (Found: Br, 65·1. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{NBr}_3$ requires Br, 65·2 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative was obtained as needles, m. p. 139° (Found: Br, 55·6. $C_{10}H_8O_3 NBr_3$ requires Br, 55·8 per cent).

Anhydrodibromalformamide.—Bromalformamide (3 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (1%, 50 c.c.), and acetic anhydride was added to it at 0° slowly with shaking until the mixture remained faintly acidic. The mixture was then left in the refrigerator overnight. It crystallised as thin plates from dilute alcohol, charring at 160° and melting at 170°. (Found: Br, 75·6. $C_6H_6O_3N_2Br_6$ requires Br, 75·7 per cent). All the anhydro derivatives of the remaining bromalamides are similarly obtained.

β-Tribromo-α-chloroethylformamide.—Bromalformamide (5 g.) was mixed with phosphorus pentachloride (2·9 g.) in a tube fitted with calcium chloride tube and heated until the evolution of hydrogen chloride slackened. The product was obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 80°/15 mm. ($C_3H_3ONClBr_3$ requires Halogen, 80·0. Found: Halogen, 79·9 per cent). The other chloro compounds are similarly prepared.

Methylbromalacetamide.—Bromalacetamide (5 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (1%, 50 c.c.), and excess of dimethyl sulphate (6-8g.) was slowly added in the cold. The final mixture should remain fairly alkaline. The oily matter separating solidified on keeping in the refrigerator for 12 hours. It was obtained as thick plates from methylated spirit, m.p. 106°. (Found: Br, 67·8. $C_5H_8O_2NBr_3$ requires Br, 67·8 per cent). The other methoxy derivatives are obtained similarly.

β-Dibromoethyleneacetamide.—As bromalacetamide when reduced with zinc dust and glacial acetic acid decomposed, its acetyl derivative was reduced. After reduction was complete, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate, after neutralisation with sodium carbonate paste at 0°, gave a solid. It was obtained as long rectangular plates from petroleum ether, m.p. 82°, yield 1 g. from 15 g. of acetyl bromalacetamide. (Found: Br, 65·5. $C_4H_5ONBr_2$ requires Br, 65·8 per cent).

All the corresponding derivatives of the bromalamides are obtained similarly and possess similar properties. The reduction products of the group (i) are less stable than those of the group (ii) and the yield increases as we ascend the series.

β-Bromoethyleneisovaleramide.—Bromalisovaleramide (15 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (150 c.c.) and zinc dust (about 6 g.) was added to it in portions. After each addition of zinc dust

the reduction mixture must be cooled. The mixture was shaken for about 4 hours, filtered and the filtrate was mixed with crushed ice and neutralised with sodium carbonate paste at 0°. On keeping the neutral mixture in the refrigerator overnight, a solid separated which was filtered at once and kept on a porous plate and purified in the refrigerator. The product is unstable at ordinary temperature but remains unchanged for a number of days in the refrigerator, Long needles, m.p. 71-74°. (Found: Br, 38.9. $C_7H_{12}ONBr$ requires. Br, 38.8 per cent).

The corresponding reduction products of the higher bromalamides are obtained in a similar way and have similar properties. The other new compounds prepared are summarised in the Tables.

TABLE I.

Name.	Formula.	Appearance.	M. p. or b. p.	Found.	Analysis.	Calc.
Benzoylbromalacetamide	$C_{11}H_{10}O_3NBr_3$	Needles	122°	Br, 53.9%		54.1%
Anhydrodibromalacetamide	$C_8H_{10}O_3N_2Br_6$	Silky needles	183-85°	72.3		72.5
β -Tribromo- α -chloroethyl-acetamide	$C_4H_5ONClBr_3$	Colourless liquid	76°/8 mm.	Halogen, 76.8		76.8
β -Tribromo- α -chloroethyl-acetylchlorimide	$C_4H_4NCl_2Br_3$	Colourless liquid	138°/25 mm.	82.2		82.5
Bromalpropionamide	$C_5H_8O_2NBr_3$	Rectangular plates	174°	Br, 67.7		67.8
Acetylbromalpropionamide	$C_7H_{10}O_3NBr_3$	Plates	96-98°	60.3		60.6
Benzoylbromalpropionamide	$C_{12}H_{12}O_3NBr_3$	Plates	113-15°	52.3		52.4
Methylbromalpropionamide	$C_6H_{10}O_2NBr_3$	Thick plates	85-87°	65.1		65.2
Anhydrodibromalpropionamide	$C_{10}H_{14}O_3N_2Br_6$	Silky needles	192°	69.3		69.5
β -Tribromo- α -chloroethyl-propionamide	$C_5H_7ONClBr_3$	Colourless liquid	120°/19 mm.	Halogen, 73.7		73.9
Acetylbromalbutyramide	$C_8H_{12}O_3NBr_3$	Thin plates	96-98°	Br, 58.5		58.5
Benzoylbromalbutyramide	$C_{13}H_{14}O_3NBr_3$	Thin plates	122°	50.6		50.8
Methylbromalbutyramide	$C_7H_{12}O_2NBr_3$	Short needles	101°	62.7		62.8

TABLE I (contd).

Name.	Formula	Appearance.	M.p. or b.p.	Found.	Analysis.	Calc.
Anhydrodibromalbutyramide	$C_{12}H_{18}O_3N_2Br_6$	Silky needles	155°	Br, 66.8%		66.8%
8-Tribromo- α -chloroethyl- butyramide	$C_6H_9ONClBr_3$	Colourless liquid	126°/15 mm.	Halogen, 71.2		71.3
Bromaliso-butyramide	$C_6H_{10}O_2NBr_3$	Shining plates	156°	Br, 65.3		65.2
Acetylbromaliso-butyramide	$C_8H_{12}O_3NBr_3$	Shining tufts	141-43°	58.5		58.5
Benzoylbromaliso-butyramide	$C_{13}H_{14}O_3NBr_3$	Shining tufts	131-32°	50.6		50.8
Methylbromaliso-butyramide	$C_7H_{12}O_2NBr_3$	Needles	135°	62.6		62.8
Anhydrodibromaliso-butyramide	$C_{12}H_{18}O_3N_2Br_6$	Silky needles	155°	66.7		66.8
Bromaliso-valeramide	$C_7H_{12}O_2NBr_3$	Sparkling plates	149°	62.7		62.8
Acetylbromaliso-valeramide	$C_9H_{14}O_3NBr_3$	Shining tufts	140-42°	56.5		56.6
Benzoylbromaliso-valeramide	$C_{14}H_{16}O_3NBr_3$	Shining tufts	98-100°	49.2		49.4
Methylbromaliso-valeramide	$C_8H_{14}O_2NBr_3$	Long rectangular plates	115-17°	60.5		60.6
Anhydrodibromaliso-valeramide	$C_{14}H_{22}O_3N_2Br_6$	Shining needles	130-32°	64.1		64.3
Bromalcapronamide	$C_8H_{14}O_2NBr_3$	Thin shining plates	146°	60.5		60.6
Acetylbromalcapronamide	$C_{10}H_{16}O_3NBr_3$	Shining tufts	120-22°	54.7		54.8

Benzoylbromalcapronamide	$C_{15}H_{18}O_3NBr_3$	Thin plates	132-34°	Br, 47.8	48.0
Methylbromalcapronamide	$C_9H_{16}O_2NBr_3$	Long rectangular plates	105.07°	58.6	58.5
Anhydrodibromalcapronamide	$C_{16}H_{28}O_3N_2Br_6$	Silky needles	163°	61.8	62.0
*Bromal-onanthamide	$C_9H_{16}O_2NBr_3$	Thin shining plates	142°	58.4	58.5
Acetylbromal onanthamide	$C_{11}H_{18}O_3NBr_3$	Shining needles	135-36°	53.0	53.1
Benzoylbromal onanthamide	$C_{16}H_{20}O_3NBr_3$	Thin plates	126°	46.5	46.7
Methylbromal onanthamide	$C_{10}H_{18}O_2NBr_3$	Long rectangular plates	93-95°	56.6	56.6
Bromalcaprylamide	$C_{10}H_{18}O_2NBr_3$	Shining thin plates	139°	56.4	56.6
Acetylbromalcaprylamide	$C_{12}H_{20}O_3NBr_3$	Silky needles	129°	51.4	51.5
Benzoylbromalcaprylamide	$C_{17}H_{22}O_3NBr_3$	Shining tufts	108-10°	45.3	45.5
Methylbromalcaprylamide	$C_{11}H_{20}O_2NBr_3$	Long plates	85°	54.6	54.8
Anhydrodibromalcaprylamide	$C_{20}H_{34}O_3N_2Br_6$	Silky needles	166°	57.8	57.8
*Bromalpelargonamide	$C_{11}H_{20}O_2NBr_3$	Shining thin plates	139°	54.6	54.8
Acetylbromalpelargonamide	$C_{13}H_{22}O_3NBr_3$	Silky needles	121°	50.2	50.0
Benzoylbromalpelargonamide	$C_{18}H_{24}O_3NBr_3$	Shining tufts	123-26°	44.1	44.3
Methylbromalpelargonamide	$C_{12}H_{22}O_2NBr_3$	Needles	72-74°	53.0	53.1

* The anhydro-derivative could not be prepared owing to the formation of a thick paste.

TABLE II.

Name.	Formula.	Appearance.	M. p.	Found.	Calc.
β -Dibromoethylenepropionamide	$C_5H_7ONBr_2$	Long rectangular plates	84—86°	Br, 61.9%	62.2%
β -Dibromoethylenebutylamide	$C_6H_9ONBr_2$	Fine needles	78—80°	58.8	59.0
β -Dibromoethylenoisobutylamide	$C_6H_9ONBr_2$	Plates	80—82°	58.7	59.0
β -Dibromoethylenoisovaleramide	$C_7H_{11}ONBr_2$	Needles	68—70°	Br, 56.0	56.1
β -Dibromoethylenecapronamide	$C_8H_{13}ONBr_2$	Long needles	74—75°	53.2	53.5
β -Bromoethylenecapronamide	$C_8H_{14}ONBr$	Shining needles	61—63°	36.2	36.4
β -Dibromoethylenecaprylamide	$C_{10}H_{17}ONBr_2$	Tufts	115°	48.9	48.9
β -Bromoethylenecaprylamide	$C_{10}H_{18}ONBr$	Shining needles	67—71°	31.9	32.2
β -Dibromoethylenepelargonamide	$C_{11}H_{19}ONBr_2$	Shining tufts	63—64°	46.9	46.9
β -Bromoethylenepelargonamide	$C_{11}H_{20}ONBr$	Colourless liquid	b. p. 148°/10 m.m.	30.2	30.5

Both the reduction products of onanthamide could not be prepared owing to the decomposition of the products.

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